

DISMANTLING EUROCENTRIC BEAUTY: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF TEHREEK-E-BANO'S 'SONG OF THE FLOWERS' CAMPAIGN

Mariyah Qayyum

Foundation University

mariaqayyum11@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Mariyah Qayyum

Abstract

Fashion brands have long used Eurocentric models of beauty in their advertisements and promotions, which have reinforced stereotypical beauty norms within society. In recent years, Pakistani brands have addressed this issue by introducing creative social media advertisement which deconstructed the Eurocentric ideas of beauty, identity and representation and promoted body positivity and cultural diversity. Similarly, Tehreek e Bano stood out as a brand which challenged and deconstructed the traditional beauty standards through its campaign "Songs of the flower". A number of research has been conducted on the Pakistani brands through the lens of commodified feminism, post-colonial identity but there is inadequate research analysing the campaign "Songs of the flower" through CDA. Therefore by utilizing Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) as both an analytical method and theoretical framework, this study aims to analyze campaign "Song of the Flowers" demonstrating how language is used to reconstruct the alternative narratives around body image, beauty and identity. The findings of this study reveals that Tehreek-e-Bano's campaign employs poetic metaphors, intertextual references and inclusive linguistic strategies to dismantle Eurocentric beauty norms which results in creation of a discourse that promotes dignity, individuality and cultural legitimacy.

1- INTRODUCTION

Decades ago, brands used to rely on traditional advertising methods, such as billboards featuring models who were presented as appealing to consumer and customers. These branding often commodified the Eurocentric beauty standards in the society, creating social and cultural stereotypes. With the advent of social media, the advertisement campaigns went through transformation as people began to disassociate themselves with brands promoting "Stereotypical beauty standards". According to Ahmed (2024) the use of social media "surged" among Pakistani consumers that resulted in awareness of various stereotypical advertisement norms. Many

campaigns started to counter the "Eurocentric stereotypical" beauty standards. According to Khan (2020) this act of countering narrow western-centric beauty standard "Fostered cultural pride and representation". For e.g Khaadi's "Wear Yourself campaign" featured models with natural skin textures, body shapes and imperfections without any retouching or aesthetic filters. They included women with diverse body types and shapes, but Tehreek e Bano's "Song of the flowers" campaign inculcated women with Down syndrome to challenge stereotypical beauty norms prevalent in fashion and media industry. This campaign aligned with global

body positivity movements that encouraged self-acceptance and inclusivity. It also sparked criticism of dominant western beauty norms and created a discourse which re-established alternative narratives around women's beauty on social media. According to Van Dijk (1990), people who control the means of discourse have the power to "control mindset". This discourse reframed the concept of beauty in many young minds. A clear gap in literature exists, as previous studies primarily examine how feminist ideals are commodified by brands to market beauty products. According to Rubab et al. (2021), beauty brands co-opt feminist ideals to drive sale; however, their study relies mainly on semiotic analysis. In previous researches, CDA has been applied to beautification creams like Fair & Lovely. According to Raza and Qasim (2025), advertisements for 'Glow & Lovely' reveal a shift toward traditional beauty norms. These researches are confined to fairness products, overlooking the broader fashion campaigns and ignoring the inclusive initiatives of major fashion brands. Moreover, there is little attention to the promotion of body diversity that challenge Eurocentric norms with the help of language which means that limited CDA analysis has been used to study fashion campaigns in Pakistan. Moreover, previous researches apply CDA mostly as an analytical method which leaves a gap in its application as a holistic framework. This Research utilizes three CDA approaches to provide a multi-dimensional analysis of the discourse. Fairclough's three dimensional model is applied to examine captions at a textual, discursive and social levels. Similarly, Van Dijk's socio cognitive approach is employed to uncover ideological structure behind representations of beauty, femininity and disability showing how these reflect and reinforce societal norms. The findings of this study will be essential for conducting seminars aimed at body positivity and cultural inclusivity along with providing further opportunities for the researchers to explore the dimensions of CDA applicable on media horizons.

1.1. Problem Statement

Existence of dominant beauty norms in Pakistani media has marginalized individuals with disability which reinforced the Eurocentric beauty norms as the normative standard. In Recent years, fashion

campaigns have started to challenge these traditional dominant norms through inclusive representations. Similarly, Tehreek e Bano's campaign "Song of the Flowers" also challenges these stereotypical norms. But, there is inadequate research that applies a CDA to such campaigns. Therefore, this study aims to analyze Tehreek e Bano's campaign "Song of the Flowers" through a Critical Discourse Analysis.

1.2. Research Aim

This study aims to analyze Tehreek e Bano's campaign "Song of the Flowers". The research intends to do that by applying a Critical Discourse Analysis to the captions of the campaign.

1.3. Research Objectives

- To examine the construction and contestation of dominant beauty norms in the captions of Tehreek-e-Bano's "Song of the Flowers" campaign through the linguistic representation of girls with Down syndrome.
- To analyze the use of poetic metaphors and intertextual references, particularly to Khalil Gibran's "Song of the Flowers," in the campaign's captions for the reframing of disability, agency and identity within an inclusive beauty discourse.

1.4. Research Questions:

- 1- How the captions in Tehreek-e-Bano's "Song of the Flowers" campaign construct and challenge dominant beauty norms through their linguistic representation of girls with Down Syndrome.
- 2- In what ways do the campaign's captions use poetic metaphors and intertextual references, particularly to Khalil Gibran's "Song of the Flowers" to reframe disability, agency and identity within an inclusive beauty discourse.

1.5. Research Significance

The findings of this study will be significant in conduction of seminars aimed at body positivity, cultural inclusivity, and ethical advertising practices within the fashion industry and academic institutions. It will also be significant in broadening the academic discourse built on CDA. Moreover it will open new avenues for researchers to explore linguistic strategies in other domains such as disability representation, gender discourse, and cultural identity

in media, thereby enriching interdisciplinary scholarship.

2- LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Gauhar et al. (2024), Pakistani clothing brands utilize “Aspirational language” which results in evoking high exclusivity and luxury. By utilizing 3 dimensional CDA in her work, the author elucidates that Pakistani fashion brands adopt specific stylistic choices in captions and slogans to convey luxuriousness and exclusiveness. These practices inculcate producing and interpreting ads that align with consumer aspirations for high social status. This social practice reflects broader socio-cultural norms where luxury fashion is associated with prestige and class hierarchy.

According to Shaukat et al. (2025), language and discourse both are used to promote items and “reinforce cultural views and ideologies”. The author elucidates in her work that language utilized in advertisements is not neutral as it actively constructs meanings that shape customers’ perceptions. The discourse in beauty product advertisements serves two purposes: first, to promote the products, and second, to reinforce cultural ideologies. These advertisements often inculcate captions which involves utilization of certain words that establishes the dominant stereotypical Eurocentric norms. Such advertisements link beauty to fairness and physical perfection . The effect of this discourse can create an identity crisis, as women are reduced to object of commodification. The utilization of such linguistic strategies results in increased customer appeal because they adhere to prevailing cultural norms and values. The application of prevailing CDA in this context significantly highlights the role of these advertisements as ideological tools.

According to Cheema et al. (2025), Instagram campaigns rely on a combination of “linguistic and visual elements”. This combination results in the creation of persuasive messages. The advertisements always reflect a connection between captions and imagery. This connection enhances the overall communicative effectiveness of advertisements. The utilization of visual aesthetics which includes color schemes and composition ,results in the transformation of textual discourse, thereby attracting customers . The captions involve utilization

of emotive and provocative language which results in engagement of audiences .This engagement results in encouragement of interaction .The utilization of these multimodal strategies by brand owners are successful in assisting the brand to convey complex ideas about beauty and identity in a simplified manner. These advertisements inculcate the integration of visuals along with texts . This amalgamation of visual and text creates a narrative that resonates with the cultural and social values of consumers. The employment of CDA in these campaigns reveals the construction of joint ideological meanings. These ideological meanings are constructed by linguistic and visual elements.

Saba and Kashif (2025) elucidate in their paper that online advertisements generate discourse that goes beyond mere product promotion, embedding “cultural and social meanings”. The semiotic analysis in their study reveals the utilization of visual signs such as colors, symbols and imagery to communicate implicit messages about beauty. This study utilizes CDA along with semiotic analysis as its theoretical framework. This framework helps expose the use of advertising discourse as tool for shaping societal attitudes toward beauty and femininity. Discursive patterns in captions frequently normalize consumerist ideas and link self-worth to product usage .The study further highlights that multimodal discourse in digital advertisements perpetuates dominant cultural ideologies while appearing progressive. The language in these online advertisements is carefully crafted to align with visual cues, thereby reinforcing ideological processes.

According to Ejaz et al. (2024), Television advertisements in Pakistan often mirror the existent “socio cultural hierarchies” through the portrayal of traditional gender roles. These advertisements repeatedly depict women in a domestic settings that reinforces traditional expectations of femininity. In contrast, these advertisement depict men in authoritative or decision making roles perpetuating patriarchal norms. The language used in TV advertisement emphasizes obedience, beauty and nurturing qualities in women, further portraying them as weak and fragile. A Critical Discourse Analysis reveals that these advertisements are exploitive, as their portrayal normalize gender inequality by embedding it in everyday discourse narrative. The

study argues that advertising discourse contributes to maintaining hegemonic norms rather than challenging them.

According to Latif et al. (2024), media's role in idealizing fair skin "significantly shapes preferences in feminine identity". He states that the Language utilized in these ads uses positive adjectives like "bright," "radiant," and "beautiful" to reinforce color bias. These advertisements display certain visual cues such as lighting and skin tone editing, which further normalize fair skin as the beauty standard. He elucidates that these campaigns often link fairness to professional achievement and romantic acceptance, embedding cultural aspirations and promoting stereotypical norms. Critical Discourse Analysis of these advertisements reveals that the fairness-focused advertising constructs an ideology in which skin color determines social mobility. Consequently, this results in toxic representations which marginalize individuals with darker skin tones, creating psychological and social pressures.

The study emphasizes that such advertisements contribute to systemic colorism and gendered beauty expectations.

Mwangia and Buvárb (2024) says that social media's influence on conveying body ideals is greater than that of broadcast media, particularly concerning themes of "body positivity and advertising". He elucidates that interactions with beauty-focused social media can promote appreciation of internal and external traits, contributing to body positivity. But contrary to that, these same interactions also results in appearance comparisons that undermines self-esteem. The Sexual objectification is a prevalent issue, as visual beauty content can reduce complex identities to physical appearance. So there is a need for more longitudinal studies to understand the long-term impact of beauty content on users.

Sultana (2023) states that " Verbal structure constructs a rhetoric" in order to depict a product more fashionable than it appears . The campaigns utilize certain captions that often employ hyperbolic language to make clothing appear more fashionable than its actual quality. The utilization of Metaphors and analogies are common linguistic tools to evoke elegance and exclusivity. The discourse constructed through these advertisements strategically links fashion to cultural identity, presenting the product as

a symbol of sophistication. The utilization of Seasonal vocabulary (e.g., "summer elegance," "spring vibes" results in creation of emotional appeal and urgency. Moreover the Narrative framing in captions positions lawn collections as lifestyle choices rather than mere garments. The CDA of these advertisements reveals that these captions embed socio-economic hierarchies, associating fashion with class privilege. The study highlights how language constructs aspirational ideals, influencing consumer perceptions of status and modernity.

3- RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a qualitative methodology that focuses on understanding meanings, context and subjective interpretations by reading and analyzing the captions multiple times .The study utilizes CDA as both theoretical and analytical framework.

3.1 Data Collection

The data for this study consists of three captions retrieved from Tehreek-e-Bano's campaign named as "Song of the Flowers". This campaign was launched in June 2025 at Eid-ul-Azha. Each caption consists a photograph of girl with down syndrome. The captions were selected because they frame the visual representation of the subjects, incorporate intertextual references central to the campaign's theme and convey the brand's ideological message of inclusivity. The data includes following captions

- 1) I am a flower, born to bloom not to fit a mold,"
- 2) "They bloomed in their own time, in their own way—unapologetically,"
- 3) "I am a kind word uttered and repeated" (the latter drawn from Khalil Gibran's Songs of the Flowers).

3.2 Theoretical framework:

This study utilizes CDA as both a theoretical lens and an analytical model integrating it into a holistic approach .This study draws on the works of Norman Fairclough, Teun van Dijk and Ruth Wodak. The concepts from their approaches will be utilized to examine captions linguistically and theoretically. According to Fairclough (1995), discourse acts as a method of representation and a form of social practice. This method is "shaping and being shaped"

by power relations. He further states that the three dimensional model which includes text, discursive practice and social practice enables a comprehensive analysis of language within its social cultural context. This theoretical model leads the analysis across three levels. The textual level includes language features and is also called the Micro level. The second level is Meso level which is the discursive level. It inculcates the production through utilization of language. The third level is called Macro level that inculcates broader socio cultural structures. According to Van Dijk (1998) Ideologies are the representations that are “socially shared”. These ideologies influence discourse structures and ideological process. He further highlights the socio cognitive approach as means to uncover the role of mental model and social cognition in mediation between discourse and society. His approach provides a lens to explore the ideological structures behind representations of disability, beauty and femininity. It further shows how they reflect and reinforce the socio cultural norms. Wodak (2001) asserts that the Discourse Historical Approach integrates “historical, political and cultural contexts” to interpret discursive strategies. He further elucidates that DHA focuses on intertextuality and contextualization, that links texts to broader socio-political narratives.

3.3 Analytical Framework

The Analytical framework of this study draws on Fairclough’s three dimensional model along with van Dijk’s Socio Cognitive Approach and Wodak’s Discourse Historical Approach. At the Micro level of Fairclough’s three dimensional model (textual analysis), the study identifies and codes linguistic features in captions, for e.g adjectives describing beauty, modality like “should” and “must” and transitivity. It further examines how the captions constructs authenticity and diversity through lexical choices. Similarly at Meso Level (Discursive Practice) the study analyses the production context, revealing the framing of these captions by brands on social media platform. It further elucidates their placement as active subjects or agents despite being treated as commodities. It also examines the audience engagement through comments, shares and reactions. At Macro or social level this research connects findings to the broader societal and Eurocentric

norms in Pakistan. The findings are also connected to the cultural expectations around femininity, stigma, disability and Down syndrome. This stage places the captions within social realities and explains the role of these captions in challenging, resisting or reconfiguring power structures. The study also utilizes van Dijk’s socio cognitive approach. This approach results in identification of implicit ideologies in captions. It further examines their opposition of dominant stereotypes and explores the activation of cognitive frames in audiences. This exploration elucidates the encouragement of self-acceptance. Additionally, Wodak’s approach is applied to trace the cultural references and themes across the data. This sheds light on the legitimization of these beauty standards.

3.4 Analysis

The utilization of captions in Tehreek-e-Bano’s “*Song of the Flowers*” campaign moves beyond the mere role of being a decorative text. They function as an important ideological tools that actively reshape the societal perceptions about beauty. Pakistan’s beauty discourse reinforces these prevailing beauty standards. These beauty standards are based on Eurocentric beauty ideas of physical symmetry, able-bodiedness, fair skin and conformity to conventional feminine aesthetics. These norms result in marginalization of those individuals who do not embody these ideas. This campaign challenges all these norms, which excludes differently-abled individuals. These norms further replace Eurocentric representations with narratives of dignity and individuality. The captions utilize words like “flower”, “bloom” and “mold” to symbolize natural growth along with diversity. These words constructs a discourse that contrasts with rigid beauty norms that demand uniformity and perfection. The utilization of metaphor “I am a flower” reframes disability as a part of natural variation. This variation challenges the Eurocentric discourse that views Down Syndrome as an abnormality. According to Lakoff and Johnson (1980), mapping disability onto nature shifts perception from a medicalized identity to an aesthetic and dignified existence. The caption “I am a flower” inculcates first-person pronoun which grants a symbolic agency and self-narration, reconstructing the voice for individuals with diverse abilities. The third-person plural pronoun used in “They bloomed in

their own time” constructs a collective dominant identity while preserving individuality and resisting homogenization. The utilization of Assertive modality in “I am a flower” conveys the certainty and power in rejecting the societal narratives that frame a disabled person’s life as incomplete. The verbs like “Bloomed” position girls as agent of growth rather than piece of commodity. This contrasts with the passive constructions which are commonly found in charity based discourse . The phrase “ not to fit a mold” utilizes a negation strategy by rejecting the conformity . It establishes a resistive narrative to the imposed Eurocentric ideals of beauty . This can also be considered as a rejection of stereotypical beauty norms . The captions create semantic juxtapositions by amalgamating natural processes like blooming with artificial constructs like the concept of mold . This reconstructs the authority over manufactured ideals. Moreover ,the use of poetic language shifts the narrative away from medical discourse to aesthetic discourse by repositioning the girls as complete and naturally beautiful rather than objects to be corrected or normalized.

Analyzing the captions at Meso Level, they are strategically and linguistically crafted for social media platforms because at these platforms brevity and emotional resonance are essential for the engagement of audience. The utilization of a poetic tone aligns with Instagram’s linguistic aesthetics which enhances share ability and cultural appeal. The captions accompany images of a girls with Down Syndrome creating a multimodal discourse that reinforces inclusivity. This interplay between text and image amplifies the ideological message of diversity and authenticity. The audience interpretations are also a part of the narrative as these captions invite participatory interpretation through hashtags and comments. They enable the audience to co-construct meaning. This interaction results in transformation of the campaign from a monologic advertisement into a dialogic discourse on beauty and identity. Tehreek e Bano positions itself as a socially responsible brand. The discursive strategy differentiates it from competitors that perpetuate Eurocentric beauty norms. The commodified feminist campaigns utilizes the captions that commodify feminist ideas for profit . But these captions avoid overt product promotion. Despite that ,they prioritize ideological messaging

which signals a shift from consumerist discourse to cultural discourse.

The campaign challenges the hegemonic beauty standards which are rooted in colonial legacies. These old and ill-fitted beauty standards privilege fairness, symmetry and normative femininity .However,these campaigns destabilizes the constructed hierarchies by celebrating the difference . Moreover, the captions also resonates with global body positivity and the movement that resonates with disability. This resonance places Pakistani fashion within transnational discourses of diversity and empowerment. The utilization of “flower” and words like “bloom” results in reframing disability from a medicalized condition to a natural and aesthetic variation . This shift aligns with the contemporary disability studies that advocate for social interpretations. The discourse drafted by “ Tehreek - e - Bano” promotes values of dignity , individuality and acceptance which counters all those Eurocentric hegemonic ideologies that equate beauty with conformity and perfection . The spread of these captions on social media results in effecting the cognitive schemas of beauty among young audiences which creates inclusive attitudes and reduces stereotypical stigmas.

Traditional advertising discourse often frames disability through medical or deficit based language that reinforces stereotypical stigmas. Tehreek-e-Bano’s campaign disrupts the creation of these stigmas by adopting poetic metaphors that emphasize beauty, individuality and emotional depth . In South Asian literary and cultural traditions, flowers are used as a symbols of purity , resilience and natural diversity . The campaign invoke floral metaphors by situating girls with Down syndrome within a culturally familiar and aesthetically valued framework .Tehreek e Bano’s campaign , situates within the metaphors of Khalil Gibran’s “Songs of Flower” . This poem is associated with spirituality , human celebration and universal beauty . The name of the campaign is also “Song of the Flowers” . This intercultural reference lends cultural legitimacy and symbolic authority to the representation of disability . The captions through their poetic language reframes beauty as an affective and existential quality rather than physical ideal . The campaign aligns its message with respected cultural values that creates ideological continuity between

inclusivity and established literary traditions . This is done by embedding Gibran’s words into appealing captions. This strategy normalizes the concept of disability between the mainstream beauty discourse. The caption “I am a flower” employ’s floral metaphors that construct disability as natural diversity rather than deviation. This challenges binary notions of normal/abnormal. It propagates disability as a common acceptable phenomenon. The association of flowers with girls having Down Syndrome in the captions embeds them within a culturally valued symbol of grace and vitality as in South Asian aesthetics, flowers significantly represents beauty, purity and resilience . The phrases like “ Born to bloom” and “ In their own time” evoke organic growth . It rejects the rigid timelines imposed by societal expectation of beauty and development. It propagates beauty as a timeless trait . In addition, the choice of gentle, affirmative words such as “bloom”, “kind” and “uttered” creates an empathetic tone that contrasts with harsh medical jargons of disability discourse . This tone again reconstructs a discourse of inclusion for disabled people through lexical softness . The captions involve repeated use of “ I am” so that the statement functions as construction of performative identity that allow girls to define themselves through metaphoric beauty rather than a diagnosed label . The Eurocentric beauty standards construct a hegemonic discourse of beauty that influences models to conform to the hegemonic standards of beauty in order to look appealing . But, in Tehreek-e-Bano’s campaign the caption includes phrases like “ Not to fit a mold” which explicitly negates uniformity . It further symbolizes resistance to the prescriptive beauty standards and affirming individuality. The verbs like “Bloomed” and “uttered” signify the agency of the subjects. This establishes their identity as active agents rather than objects of commodity or disabled people. The poetic metaphors evoke emotional engagement rather than persuasion which invites audiences to feel inclusion rather than merely understand it. The language utilized in these captions resist rigid categorization which allows disability to be represented as fluid and multifaceted rather than fixed within binary oppositions. The caption “I am kind word uttered and repeated” positions the girl as a metaphorical embodiment of kindness and continuity. It shifts the focus from

physical appearance to emotional and existential worth. The words in the captions carry semantic meaning and connection. The caption constructs the identity through affective presence rather than visual perfection. This reconstructed identity challenges and demolishes the pillars of dominant beauty discourse. The verbs suggest endurance and remembrance. This endurance symbolizes the girl’s existence as active participating agent which counters the narratives that frame disability as transient or marginal. Gibran’s poetry use floral personification to represent beauty, as flowers speak as sentient beings in his poetry. The captions symbolically align the girls with these flowers, thereby providing them voice, room and authority. The discourse produced through this alignment redefines agency beyond productivity. The intertextual metaphors utilized in the captions dismantle the binaries of ability and disability; instead, they present disability as a continuous human experience. The captions avoid didactic or awareness-based language opting for gentle and reflective tones that initiate empathy and contemplation that proves to be more effective in challenging ingrained biases.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of this study reveals that caption employ metaphoric and lexical choices to dismantle deficit based narratives and constructs beauty as a natural diversity. This finding aligns with Fairclough’s textual dimension, demonstrating the role of language as a site of ideological struggle against Eurocentric stereotypical norms. The use of pronouns and active transitivity patterns position the girls with Down Syndrome as speaking subjects rather than passive objects. The discursive shifts existent within these captions reflect Van Dijks socio cognitive approach indicating a transformation in mental models that associate disability with dependency. The incorporation of Khalil Gibran’s “*Song of the Flower’s*” “functions as a discourse-historical strategy, which embeds the representation of disability within the culturally revered literary traditions. This intertextuality normalizes inclusion and reframes beauty as an affective and existential quality rather than a visual commodity required to meet Eurocentric norms. Applying CDA as an analytical as well as theoretical lens, enabled a multi-layered interpretation of captions across textual, discursive

and social dimensions . This holistic approach demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating Fairclough's , Van Dijk's and Wodak's frameworks to uncover the role of language in construction of counter discourses in fashion advertising.

5. CONCLUSION:

The findings of this study concludes that Tehreek-e-Bano's captions linguistically reconstructs beauty as diversity and authenticity which challenges the prevalent Eurocentric and ableist norms dominant within the Pakistani fashion discourse. The campaigns positions girls with down syndrome as agents of self-definition by utilization of pronouns, active verbs and metaphoric identity assertions. These captions resist deficit based narratives and promotes dignity. The integration of Khalil Gibran's poetic references situates disability within culturally respected frameworks that reinforce inclusive beauty ideals. This aligns the campaign with broader humanistic values. To sum up, the application of CDA as a holistic framework in advertising reveals how language is used in discursive constructions that facilitate ideological resistance and social transformation.

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